

Tunable High-Recall Title-and-Abstract Screening Using Meta-Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct Hidden-State Logistic Probes

Running title: Hidden-State Probes for High-Recall Screening

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Declarations

Funding	This research received no specific grant from any funding agency in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.
Conflict of interest	The author declares no conflicts of interest.
Ethics statement	This study used previously collected title-and-abstract screening datasets and did not involve direct interaction with human participants, collection of new human-subject data, or intervention with human subjects. Ethics approval was therefore not required for this secondary methodological analysis.
Data and code availability	The analysis code, reproducibility documentation, and versioned output files supporting this study are archived on Zenodo at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20176429 . The archive corresponds to GitHub repository release v1.0.1: https://github.com/baobao0605/llama-hidden-state-systematic-review-screening/tree/v1.0.1 .
Author contributions	Yongzhang Ji: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Visualization, Validation, Writing - original draft, Writing - review and editing.
Acknowledgements	The author acknowledges the developers and maintainers of the open-source software, model, and dataset resources used in this study.
Preprint statement	This is a preprint version of the manuscript and may differ from the version submitted to or accepted by a journal. The archived preprint is available at Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20220076

Abstract

Background: Title-and-abstract screening for systematic reviews is labor-intensive, and useful automation must maintain very high recall while reducing manual workload.

Objective: To test whether prompt-conditioned Llama hidden states can be converted by simple supervised linear probes into threshold-tunable inclusion scores for high-recall title-and-abstract screening.

Methods: Instead of asking an LLM API to generate final include/exclude decisions, we treated Meta-Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct as a frozen feature extractor and trained simple regularized logistic-regression probes as linear readouts from final-layer last-token hidden states to review-specific screening-stage labels. The primary setting used 4096-token inputs, short criteria prompts, class-balanced training, and stronger regularization ($C = 0.01$). We evaluated three labelled title-and-abstract screening datasets against BM25 and TF-IDF lexical baselines and characterized uncertainty and heterogeneity with bootstrap, ceiling, score-separation, in-sample linear-readout diagnostics, and supplementary robustness analyses.

Results: In the primary setting, WSS@95 was 0.751 (95% CI, 0.431-0.781) for Anmarkrud_2022, 0.715 (95% CI, 0.688-0.834) for Chan_CD011218, and 0.234 (95% CI, 0.166-0.288) for Theobald_2021. The hidden-state probe exceeded both BM25 and TF-IDF lexical baselines on the primary WSS@95 endpoint in all three datasets, although TF-IDF was a stronger lexical baseline and exceeded the probe at WSS@99 in Anmarkrud_2022. Ceiling analysis showed that the observed probe captured 86.3%, 76.9%, and 45.9% of the theoretical WSS@95 ceiling in the three datasets.

Conclusions: Prompt-conditioned Llama hidden-state probes can support recall-constrained title-and-abstract screening triage and reduce workload under reviewer-defined operating points. They should be used as decision-support tools to assist, not replace, final human screening decisions.

Keywords: systematic review screening; title-and-abstract screening; large language models; hidden states; logistic regression; WSS@95; BM25; TF-IDF; high recall

1. Introduction

Title-and-abstract screening is one of the most labor-intensive stages of systematic reviews. Sensitive search strategies are intentionally broad so that potentially eligible studies are not missed, but this also means that reviewers must manually inspect large numbers of irrelevant records before reaching a smaller set of candidate studies for full-text assessment (Page et al., 2021; O'Mara-Eves et al., 2015; Marshall & Wallace, 2019). AI-assisted screening methods have therefore attracted substantial interest as a way to prioritize records, reduce manual workload, and support evidence synthesis workflows. In this setting, however, the practical value of automation depends less on ordinary classification accuracy than on whether workload can be reduced while preserving the high sensitivity required for systematic reviews.

Because systematic reviews aim to identify as much relevant evidence as possible, the tolerance for false negatives during screening is low. Retaining an irrelevant record for human review mainly increases workload, whereas excluding an eligible record too early may remove relevant evidence from the review altogether. Screening support tools should therefore be evaluated under explicit high-recall

constraints. Work saved over sampling at fixed recall levels, such as $WSS@95$, was developed for this purpose: it measures workload reduction beyond random exclusion while maintaining a target level of recall (Cohen et al., 2006). The methodological problem is therefore not simply to produce an include/exclude prediction, but to produce a screening signal that can be adjusted to meet recall targets such as 95% or 99%.

Recent work has explored the use of large language models for title-and-abstract screening through API-based prompting, structured-output prompting, and prompt-policy designs (Ji & Xu, 2026). These approaches are natural starting points because they can ask a model to directly label a record as include or exclude, or to provide a confidence-like response. However, direct prompting is not naturally organized around recall-constrained threshold selection. Generated include/exclude outputs are fixed decisions rather than threshold-sweepable scores; prompted outputs can be sensitive to wording, prompt templates, and output policies (Chatterjee et al., 2024); and API-returned token log probabilities, when available, are generation-token quantities rather than review-specific supervised inclusion scores trained against screening-stage labels (OpenAI, n.d.; DeepSeek, n.d.). They should therefore not be assumed to provide calibrated, stable operating scores for $WSS@95$ or $WSS@99$ threshold selection (Lovering et al., 2024).

The present study evaluates this representation-to-score alternative. Instead of asking an LLM to generate final screening decisions, we use Meta-Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct as a frozen feature extractor. For each record, the title-and-abstract text is combined with a review-specific criteria prompt, and the final-layer hidden state at the last token is extracted as a task-conditioned representation of the formatted input. A simple regularized logistic-regression probe is then trained as a linear readout from hidden states to screening-stage labels. This constrained supervised head was chosen so that the workflow tests whether screening-relevant structure is readable from the frozen representation rather than shifting the task to a complex nonlinear downstream classifier. The resulting review-specific inclusion scores can be swept across thresholds to select high-recall operating points.

We evaluated this approach on three title-and-abstract screening datasets: Anmarkrud_2022, Chan_CD011218, and Theobald_2021. The primary question was whether prompt-conditioned LLM hidden-state logistic-regression probes could produce threshold-sweepable inclusion scores that reduce manual screening workload under high-recall constraints. We compared the hidden-state probe with BM25 and TF-IDF lexical baselines, evaluated workload reduction using $WSS@95$ and $WSS@99$, and reported AUROC and average precision as complementary ranking metrics. We further used bootstrap

confidence intervals, pipeline-matched shuffle-label controls, ceiling analysis, score-separation diagnostics, Llama-BM25/TF-IDF score relationships, and representation-capacity diagnostics to assess uncertainty, robustness, and dataset heterogeneity.

2. Methods

2.1 Methodological objective: threshold-sweepable inclusion scoring

The methodological objective of this study was to obtain a threshold-sweepable inclusion score for each title-and-abstract record, rather than a single direct include/exclude decision. This distinction follows from the practical goal of systematic-review screening. At the title-and-abstract stage, useful automation should reduce manual workload while preserving very high recall. A screening method therefore needs to rank records by their likelihood of inclusion and allow the decision threshold to be adjusted so that operating points with prespecified recall targets, such as 95% or 99%, can be selected. The primary target of the workflow was therefore not ordinary binary classification accuracy, but recall-constrained workload reduction based on graded inclusion scores.

Direct API-based prompting offers a natural way to apply large language models to screening, but it does not directly solve this scoring problem. A prompted model can generate an include/exclude decision, a confidence-like statement, or, in some systems, token-level log probability information. However, these outputs are not review-specific supervised inclusion scores trained against screening-stage labels. API-returned log probabilities are generation-token quantities, exposed for message content tokens and limited top-token alternatives, rather than supervised probabilities learned from the review's own INCLUDE and EXCLUDE decisions (OpenAI, n.d.; DeepSeek, n.d.). In addition, prior work has shown that LLM outputs can be sensitive to prompt wording and templates, and that language-model output probabilities may be poorly calibrated in simple probabilistic settings (Chatterjee et al., 2024; Lovering et al., 2024). For these reasons, we did not treat direct prompting decisions, prompted confidence statements, or API token log probabilities as the primary screening score.

We instead used a decomposed representation-to-score workflow with three stages. First, Meta-Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct was used as a frozen representation model. For each record, the title-and-abstract text was combined with a review-specific criteria prompt, and the model's final-layer hidden state at the last token was extracted as a task-conditioned representation of that formatted input. Second, a simple regularized logistic-regression probe was trained as a linear readout from the hidden-state representation to the review-specific screening-stage label. This supervised readout produced a graded inclusion score

for each record, rather than a generated screening decision. Third, these inclusion scores were swept across candidate thresholds to select recall-constrained operating points, including WSS@95 and WSS@99. Thus, the LLM supplied the representation, the linear probe supplied the supervised review-specific score, and the threshold sweep translated that score into an operating point aligned with the screening objective.

The remaining Methods sections define each component of this workflow and its evaluation. Section 2.2 describes the datasets and screening-stage labels. Section 2.3 describes the construction of task-conditioned inputs. Section 2.4 defines hidden-state representation extraction, and Section 2.5 defines the regularized logistic-regression readout. Section 2.6 describes threshold sweeps and recall-constrained workload-saving metrics. Section 2.7 defines the BM25 and TF-IDF lexical baselines under the same threshold-sweep framework. Section 2.8 describes uncertainty and shuffle-label robustness analyses. Section 2.9 describes dataset heterogeneity and representation diagnostics, including full-sample linear readout and strict in-sample linear separability analyses used to assess whether screening-stage labels were linearly readable from the hidden-state feature space.

2.2 Datasets and screening-stage labels

We evaluated the workflow on three labelled title-and-abstract screening datasets: Anmarkrud_2022, Chan_CD011218, and Theobald_2021. The Anmarkrud_2022 and Theobald_2021 datasets were derived from educational and psychological systematic-review screening collections described by Campos et al. (2024). The Chan_CD011218 dataset was derived from the Mendeley Data release by Chan, He, Leung, and Verspoor (2024) and the associated dataset paper by Chan et al. (2025). The three datasets differed in sample size, INCLUDE prevalence, and apparent screening difficulty, allowing the workflow to be evaluated across heterogeneous title-and-abstract screening conditions.

Each record was represented as a binary title-and-abstract screening item. The positive class was INCLUDE, and the negative class was EXCLUDE. All recall, false-negative, and workload-saving metrics were defined with INCLUDE as the positive class, because the primary safety concern in title-and-abstract screening is missing records that should remain in the review pipeline.

The reference labels were treated as title-and-abstract screening-stage labels rather than downstream post-full-text eligibility labels. This distinction was important because the model input was restricted to title-and-abstract information. Full-text eligibility decisions may depend on information unavailable in the title and abstract; using such decisions as the primary reference labels would unfairly

penalize a title-and-abstract screening model for evidence it could not observe. The analysis therefore evaluated whether the workflow could reproduce and prioritize screening-stage decisions based on the information available at the title-and-abstract stage.

Table 1. Dataset characteristics.

Dataset	Records,n	Included,n	Excluded,n	Included,%	Role in analysis
Anmarkrud_2022	2502	212	2290	8.50%	large imbalanced review
Chan_CD011218	690	14	676	2.00%	rare-positive stress test
Theobald_2021	518	240	278	46.30%	complex eligibility-criteria stress test

2.3 Task-conditioned input construction

For each record, we constructed a formatted input sequence containing two components: the candidate record content and the review-specific task context. The candidate record content consisted of the record’s title-and-abstract text. The task context was supplied by a review-specific criteria prompt. Combining these two components allowed the hidden state to be extracted from an input sequence that represented the record in the context of the review’s screening criteria.

The criteria prompt was used to condition the hidden-state representation, not to elicit a generated include/exclude decision. It was not used as an outcome label, and the LLM was not prompted to produce a screening decision. Instead, the model was run so that the formatted title/abstract-plus-criteria sequence could be passed through the frozen LLM, after which the hidden-state representation was extracted for downstream supervised readout.

We evaluated short and full criteria prompts. Short criteria prompts were AI-assisted but researcher-curated concise summaries of the review-specific inclusion context. Full-criteria prompts were manually structured from review-specific reported eligibility criteria. Exact prompt text is provided in Supplementary Table S1 and Supplementary Data 1. The short-criteria setting was used as the primary prompt condition because it provided the strongest high-recall workload-saving performance in the prompt-length ablation analyses.

2.4 Hidden-state representation extraction

Meta-Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct was used as a frozen causal language model feature extractor. This model is a relatively lightweight open-weight LLM compared with larger frontier systems, making

hidden-state extraction feasible in suitable local or institutional compute environments. In a causal language model, each token representation is formed from the preceding context; therefore, the final-token representation is conditioned on the full formatted input available to the model.

For each record, the formatted input consisted of the title-and-abstract text together with the review-specific criteria prompt. The model was run in forward-pass mode only, without text generation and without fine-tuning. We extracted the final-layer hidden state at the final token position so that the representation reflected the candidate record in the context of the review-specific criteria.

The maximum input length was 4096 tokens. Inputs longer than this limit were truncated by the tokenizer. This token limit is distinct from the dimensionality of the hidden-state vector. For record i , let x_i denote the tokenized title/abstract-plus-criteria input, and let T_i denote the final token position after tokenization and truncation. We extracted:

$$h_i = H_{\text{final}}(x_i, T_i), h_i \in \mathbb{R}^{4096}$$

Here, h_i is a 4096-dimensional vector because Meta-Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct represents each token position with a 4096-dimensional hidden state. The individual dimensions of this vector were treated as latent coordinates rather than human-defined eligibility variables. We therefore did not interpret single hidden-state dimensions directly. The assumption was more limited: if screening-relevant signal is present in the prompt-conditioned representation, a supervised readout may be able to learn from the full vector.

2.5 Logistic-regression probing and regularized inclusion scoring

The hidden-state vector h_i is a task-conditioned representation, not a screening decision and not a similarity score. We therefore trained a supervised probe to map each 4096-dimensional hidden-state vector to the corresponding screening-stage label. The goal of this readout step was to convert the frozen Llama representation into a graded inclusion score that could later be ranked and swept across thresholds.

Logistic regression was deliberately chosen as a simple linear readout. We did not use a multilayer nonlinear classifier on top of the hidden states, because a more expressive downstream head could learn additional task structure and make it harder to determine whether screening-relevant information was already linearly readable from the frozen hidden-state space. The logistic-regression probe therefore

served as a constrained supervised head: it tested whether the prompt-conditioned hidden-state representation contained label-related structure that could be read out by a regularized linear decision boundary. This design made the readout more auditable, while recognizing that the hidden-state dimensions themselves remained latent and were not directly interpretable eligibility variables.

The screening-stage label was coded as

$$y_i = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if record } i \text{ was labelled INCLUDE,} \\ 0, & \text{if record } i \text{ was labelled EXCLUDE.} \end{cases}$$

For each record, the logistic-regression probe learned a weight vector $w \in \mathbb{R}^{4096}$ and an intercept b . It first computed a linear score:

$$z_i = w^\top h_i + b.$$

This score was then transformed by the logistic function into a value between 0 and 1:

$$p_i = \sigma(z_i) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-z_i)}.$$

We used p_i as the graded inclusion score. Higher values indicated stronger evidence toward the INCLUDE class according to the supervised probe. This score was used for ranking and threshold sweeping; it was not treated as a perfectly calibrated probability or as a final screening decision.

The probe learned w and b by fitting the predicted inclusion scores p_i to the screening-stage labels y_i . Because INCLUDE records were rare in two of the three datasets, we used `class_weight="balanced"` so that errors on INCLUDE records contributed more strongly during fitting and the training objective was not dominated by the majority EXCLUDE class.

The model was L2-regularized, meaning that large weights were penalized during training. The regularization parameter C controlled how strongly the learned linear readout was constrained. In scikit-learn's logistic-regression implementation, C is inversely related to regularization strength:

$C \downarrow \Rightarrow$ stronger regularization $\Rightarrow \|w\|_2 \downarrow \Rightarrow$ more constrained linear readout.

$C \uparrow \Rightarrow$ weaker regularization $\Rightarrow \|w\|_2 \uparrow \Rightarrow$ more flexible linear readout.

We compared $C = 0.01$ and $C = 1.0$. The $C = 0.01$ setting imposed stronger regularization and therefore tested a more constrained readout from the hidden-state space. The $C = 1.0$ setting allowed a more flexible linear readout. The primary analysis used $C = 0.01$, corresponding to the configuration selected by the prompt-length and regularization ablation results.

Model performance was estimated using stratified five-fold cross-validation. Within each fold, feature standardization and logistic-regression fitting were performed only on the training split. The fitted scaler and probe were then applied to the held-out split to generate inclusion scores for records not used in fitting that fold. Concatenating the held-out predictions across folds yielded one out-of-fold inclusion score p_i for every record. These out-of-fold scores were used for threshold sweeping, WSS@95 and WSS@99 calculation, AUROC, average precision, and subsequent diagnostic analyses.

2.6 Threshold sweeps and recall-constrained workload-saving metrics

The logistic-regression probe produced one out-of-fold inclusion score p_i for each record. These scores were not evaluated only at a default threshold such as 0.5, because the practical objective was not ordinary binary classification. Instead, the goal was to identify operating points that preserved very high recall while assigning as many records as possible below the screening threshold. We therefore swept candidate thresholds across the observed score range.

At a given threshold τ , records with scores greater than or equal to τ were classified as predicted INCLUDE, and records with scores below τ were classified as predicted EXCLUDE:

$$\hat{y}_i(\tau) = \begin{cases} 1, & p_i \geq \tau, \\ 0, & p_i < \tau. \end{cases}$$

Here, $\hat{y}_i(\tau) = 1$ denotes predicted INCLUDE and $\hat{y}_i(\tau) = 0$ denotes predicted EXCLUDE. These machine-predicted labels were compared with the human screening-stage labels y_i , where INCLUDE was the positive class and EXCLUDE was the negative class.

Machine-predicted \ Human label	Human label: INCLUDE	Human label: EXCLUDE
	Predicted INCLUDE	True positive, $TP(\tau)$
Predicted EXCLUDE	False negative, $FN(\tau)$	True negative, $TN(\tau)$

All threshold-specific quantities were calculated from this 2×2 comparison between predicted labels and human screening-stage labels.

Recall, also referred to as sensitivity, measured the proportion of human-labelled INCLUDE records retained at threshold τ . This was the primary safety constraint, because false negatives correspond to INCLUDE records assigned below the screening threshold:

$$\text{Recall}(\tau) = \frac{TP(\tau)}{TP(\tau) + FN(\tau)}.$$

Specificity measured the proportion of human-labelled EXCLUDE records assigned to predicted EXCLUDE:

$$\text{Specificity}(\tau) = \frac{TN(\tau)}{TN(\tau) + FP(\tau)}.$$

Specificity describes correct exclusion among negative records, but it does not directly express how much screening workload would be reduced. We therefore calculated the work-saved rate, defined as the proportion of all records assigned to predicted EXCLUDE at threshold τ :

$$\text{WorkSaved}(\tau) = \frac{TN(\tau) + FN(\tau)}{N}.$$

Here, N is the total number of records in the dataset. Because $FN(\tau)$ appears in the numerator, work saved must always be interpreted together with an explicit recall constraint. A high work-saved rate is useful only when the number of missed INCLUDE records remains within the review team's tolerance.

Work saved over sampling at a target recall level r , denoted $\text{WSS}@r$, subtracts the amount of work that could be saved by randomly excluding $1 - r$ of records while maintaining recall r . It therefore measures workload reduction beyond random exclusion under an explicit high-recall constraint:

$$\text{WSS}@r = \text{WorkSaved}(\tau_r) - (1 - r).$$

For each dataset and method, the selected threshold τ_r was the threshold that maximized work saved while satisfying the corresponding recall constraint:

$$\tau_r = \arg \max_{\tau: \text{Recall}(\tau) \geq r} \text{WorkSaved}(\tau).$$

The reported $\text{WSS}@r$ value was the WSS value at this selected threshold. In this study, we evaluated two target recall levels: $r = 0.95$, corresponding to $\text{WSS}@95$, and $r = 0.99$, corresponding to $\text{WSS}@99$. Thus, $\text{WSS}@95$ and $\text{WSS}@99$ were threshold-selected operating-point metrics, not metrics evaluated at a default classification threshold.

All threshold-specific operating-point quantities reported in the Results were calculated at the selected thresholds. For example, $\text{Recall}@95$, $\text{Specificity}@95$, $\text{Work saved}@95$, $\text{TP}@95$, and $\text{FN}@95$ refer to recall, specificity, work-saved rate, true positives, and false negatives at the selected $\text{WSS}@95$ threshold. Analogous definitions were used for the $\text{WSS}@99$ operating point. This threshold-sweep procedure operationalized the central screening objective of the study: using graded inclusion scores to choose operating points that preserved very high recall while maximizing workload reduction under the specified recall constraint.

2.7 Lexical baselines and complementary ranking metrics

To assess whether the hidden-state probe provided screening utility beyond lexical matching, we compared it with two lexical baselines: BM25 and TF-IDF. Both baselines used the review-specific criteria text as the query and the record’s title-and-abstract text as the document. Their scores were treated in the same way as the Llama hidden-state probe scores: thresholds were swept across each score range, and WSS@95 and WSS@99 were calculated using the recall-constrained procedure defined in Section 2.6.

BM25 is a classical lexical retrieval method that scores a document by how strongly its terms match a query, while accounting for term informativeness and document length (Robertson & Zaragoza, 2009). In this study, BM25 served as a transparent term-matching baseline, scoring each title-and-abstract record against the review-specific criteria text.

TF-IDF represents text by giving higher weight to terms that are frequent in a document but relatively uncommon across the corpus (Salton & Buckley, 1988). In this study, TF-IDF served as a stronger lexical vector-space baseline, comparing the weighted term profile of each title-and-abstract record with the weighted term profile of the criteria text.

For both lexical baselines, higher scores indicated stronger lexical relevance to the review criteria. These baseline scores were not treated as final screening decisions. Instead, they were evaluated under the same threshold-sweep framework as the hidden-state probe. When differences from lexical baselines were reported, they were calculated as the hidden-state probe’s WSS value minus the corresponding BM25 or TF-IDF WSS value under the same recall constraint. Positive differences indicate greater recall-constrained workload saving by the hidden-state probe.

In addition to WSS@95 and WSS@99, we reported AUROC and average precision as complementary ranking metrics. AUROC summarizes how well a score separates positive from negative records across possible thresholds (Fawcett, 2006). Average precision summarizes how well positive records are concentrated near the top of a ranked list and is especially informative when positives are rare (Davis & Goadrich, 2006). These metrics describe overall ranking quality, whereas WSS@95 and WSS@99 define the primary recall-constrained workload-saving endpoints.

2.8 Uncertainty and robustness analyses

Point estimates alone do not show how stable a screening metric is under sampling variation. This was especially important because the three datasets differed in sample size and INCLUDE prevalence. We therefore used record-level bootstrap resampling to quantify uncertainty around the reported workload-saving and ranking metrics.

Record-level bootstrap resampling estimates uncertainty by repeatedly drawing records with replacement from the observed dataset. For each dataset and method, we generated 1000 bootstrap samples. In each bootstrap replicate, the relevant metric was recalculated using the same threshold-sweep procedure used in the main analysis. We reported 95% percentile confidence intervals for WSS@95, WSS@99, AUROC, and average precision.

We also performed a pipeline-matched shuffle-label control as a supplementary robustness check. This analysis addressed a different question from bootstrap resampling. Bootstrap intervals describe sampling uncertainty under the observed label structure, whereas shuffle-label controls test whether similar performance could arise after breaking the relationship between records and human screening-stage labels. This was important because the hidden-state features were high-dimensional and the downstream probe was supervised.

In the shuffle-label control, the human screening-stage labels were randomly permuted while the hidden-state feature matrix was held fixed. The same standardization, logistic-regression fitting, class weighting, regularization setting, cross-validation procedure, threshold sweep, and metric calculations were then repeated on the permuted labels. Empirical one-sided p-values were calculated as the proportion of shuffled-label replicates that matched or exceeded the observed metric value, using a plus-one correction. This analysis was interpreted as a supplementary sanity check, not as the primary performance endpoint. Its purpose was to test whether the observed hidden-state probe performance depended on the real record-label association rather than being reproduced by the modeling pipeline under randomized labels.

2.9 Dataset heterogeneity and representation diagnostics

Because workload-saving performance varied across datasets, we conducted additional diagnostic analyses to characterize dataset-level limits, score behavior, and hidden-state representation structure. These analyses were descriptive and were not used to define the primary performance endpoint. Their

purpose was to help interpret why the hidden-state probe produced stronger workload-saving results in some datasets than in others.

First, we calculated the theoretical WSS@95 ceiling for each dataset. This ceiling represents the maximum WSS@95 that could be achieved under a perfect ranking in which all INCLUDE records were ranked above all EXCLUDE records. It was used to distinguish model ranking limitations from dataset-level limits on achievable workload saving. We also calculated the observed-to-ceiling ratio:

$$\text{Observed-to-ceiling ratio} = \frac{\text{Observed WSS@95}}{\text{Maximum WSS@95}}$$

A higher ratio indicates that the hidden-state probe approached the best WSS@95 theoretically available for that dataset, whereas a lower ratio suggests that substantial ranking or separation difficulty remained.

Second, we examined score-level behavior. Score separation describes whether human-labelled INCLUDE records tend to receive higher scores than EXCLUDE records. We used score-distribution plots and summary comparisons to describe whether the hidden-state probe scores separated the two screening labels. This analysis was descriptive and was not used for threshold selection.

We also compared hidden-state probe scores with BM25 and TF-IDF scores. Pearson correlation was used to summarize linear association between score vectors, and Spearman correlation was used to summarize rank-order association. These correlations assessed whether the hidden-state probe and lexical baselines ranked records similarly. Low correlation may indicate partly different scoring behavior, whereas higher correlation suggests more overlap between hidden-state and lexical scoring signals. These correlations were not interpreted as evidence of a specific semantic mechanism inside the LLM.

Third, we conducted a representation-capacity diagnostic using full-sample linear readouts. A full-sample linear readout diagnostic fits a linear classifier using all labelled records and evaluates it in sample. In this study, it was used as an upper-bound diagnostic to test whether screening-stage labels were linearly readable from the frozen hidden-state feature space. Because the same records were used for fitting and evaluation, this analysis was not treated as out-of-fold or out-of-sample performance evidence.

We also ran a strict in-sample linear separability check. This check tested whether a hyperplane could separate INCLUDE and EXCLUDE records in the standardized full-sample hidden-state space. It was used only as a geometric representation diagnostic. A positive result indicates that the two label groups were linearly separable in sample under the implemented test, but it does not estimate generalizable screening performance or establish mechanistic understanding.

Finally, we conducted exploratory geometry diagnostics in the hidden-state feature space. The centroid separation ratio compared the distance between INCLUDE and EXCLUDE class centroids with the within-class spread of hidden-state vectors:

$$\text{Centroid separation ratio} = \frac{\text{between-class centroid distance}}{\text{within-class dispersion}}.$$

Larger values indicate greater class-level separation relative to within-class dispersion. We also used principal component analysis only to visualize low-dimensional projections of standardized hidden-state vectors. Neither centroid separation nor PCA was used for model fitting, threshold selection, or primary performance estimation. These representation diagnostics were exploratory and should not be interpreted as mechanistic evidence that the model understood eligibility criteria. Their purpose was to provide descriptive context for dataset heterogeneity and for the readability of label-related structure in the hidden-state space. The analysis scripts, versioned outputs, and reproducibility documentation corresponding to these procedures are available in the archived Zenodo release (Ji, 2026).

3. Results

3.1 Experimental overview and evidence map

The Results evaluate whether the primary hidden-state probe could convert prompt-conditioned Llama representations into threshold-tunable, recall-constrained screening scores. The primary configuration was the Meta-Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct hidden-state logistic probe using 4096-token inputs, short criteria prompts, class-balanced training, and stronger logistic-regression regularization ($C = 0.01$). This configuration combined the three components of the proposed workflow: task-conditioned hidden-state extraction, a constrained supervised linear readout, and threshold selection for high-recall workload saving.

The analyses proceed from threshold behavior to selected operating points, then to shuffle-label controls, configuration comparisons, lexical baselines, and representation diagnostics. Table 2 summarizes how each Results subsection contributes to the overall evidence chain.

Table 2. Evidence map for the Results.

The Results are organized to test whether hidden-state probes produce threshold-tunable screening scores, whether those scores yield high-recall workload savings, whether the results depend on true screening labels, whether the primary configuration is supported by ablation comparisons, whether the probe improves on lexical baselines, and how representation diagnostics explain dataset-level variation.

Evidence target	Results section	Main visual/table	What it supports
Threshold tunability	3.2	Figures 1–3	Hidden-state scores can be moved across recall–workload operating points rather than acting as fixed include/exclude decisions.
High-recall workload saving	3.3	Figures 4–5; Table 3	Threshold sweeps yield WSS@95 and WSS@99 operating points with interpretable recall, specificity, work-saved, TP, and FN values.
Dependence on true screening labels	3.4	Figures 6–7	Observed performance is not reproduced after breaking the record–label association with shuffle-label controls.
Primary configuration	3.5	Figure 8	Short criteria prompts and stronger regularization support the chosen constrained linear-readout configuration.
Lexical baseline comparison	3.6	Figures 9–10	The hidden-state probe exceeds BM25 and TF-IDF on the primary WSS@95 endpoint, while WSS@99 gives a more nuanced comparison.
Dataset heterogeneity and representation diagnostics	3.7	Figures 11–14; Table 4	Ceiling, score separation, linear readability, lexical-score relationships, and exploratory geometry help interpret variation across datasets.

We begin by testing the first requirement of the workflow: whether the primary hidden-state probe produced scores that were tunable across thresholds.

3.2 Threshold sweeps demonstrate tunable high-recall screening

The first analysis tested whether the primary hidden-state probe produced a graded score that could be moved across recall–workload operating points. This was the necessary first condition for the proposed workflow: the probe would be useful for high-recall screening only if changing the decision threshold produced meaningful changes in recall and workload reduction.

Figure 1. Threshold-dependent recall–work-saved trade-off for the primary hidden-state probe. Each panel shows the relationship between recall and work saved as the decision threshold was swept across the out-of-fold inclusion scores for one dataset. The marked points indicate the selected WSS@95 and WSS@99 operating points. Across all three datasets, changing the threshold moved the model along a recall–workload trade-off, showing that the hidden-state probe produced an adjustable screening score rather than a single fixed include/exclude decision.

Across the three datasets, threshold sweeping produced systematic recall–workload trade-offs. This supports the central use of the hidden-state probe as a tunable score: the same score could be moved toward higher recall or greater workload reduction depending on the selected operating point.

Figure 2. WSS@95 and WSS@99 across candidate thresholds. Green curves are shown only for thresholds satisfying the WSS@99 validity condition, i.e., recall ≥ 0.99 ; thresholds with lower recall were not plotted for WSS@99. For each dataset, WSS@95 and WSS@99 were calculated across candidate thresholds for the primary hidden-state probe, subject to their respective recall constraints. The marked points indicate the selected thresholds used for the reported WSS@95 and WSS@99 values. This figure shows that the final workload-saving values were derived from threshold sweeping rather than from a default classification threshold.

To show the threshold behavior more directly, we also examined the individual operating metrics across thresholds. Recall, specificity, and work saved changed together as the threshold was varied, confirming that threshold selection controlled the screening trade-off rather than merely changing a nominal class label.

Figure 3. Threshold-specific recall, specificity, and work-saved behavior by dataset.

Each panel shows how operating metrics changed as the decision threshold was swept across the primary hidden-state probe scores. Recall decreased as thresholds became more selective, while specificity and work saved generally increased. These curves provide the threshold-level basis for selecting recall-constrained operating points in later analyses.

Together, these threshold-sweep results establish that the hidden-state probe produced a genuinely adjustable inclusion score. The next section reports the selected WSS@95 and WSS@99 operating points derived from these sweeps.

3.3 Selected WSS@95 and WSS@99 operating points

After confirming that the hidden-state scores were threshold-tunable, we selected the WSS@95 and WSS@99 operating points from the threshold sweeps. WSS@95 used the threshold that maximized workload saving while maintaining recall of at least 95%; WSS@99 used the same procedure under a stricter 99% recall constraint.

Figure 4. Selected WSS@95 operating points for the primary hidden-state probe. Bars show the selected WSS@95 values for each dataset after threshold sweeping. WSS@95 was selected as the operating point that maximized workload saving while maintaining recall of at least 95%. The figure shows strong WSS@95 values in Anmarkrud_2022 and Chan_CD011218 and a smaller but positive value in Theobald_2021.

At WSS@95, the primary hidden-state probe achieved positive workload saving in all three datasets, with the strongest operating-point performance in Anmarkrud_2022 and Chan_CD011218.

Figure 5. Selected WSS@99 operating points for the primary hidden-state probe. Bars show the selected WSS@99 values for each dataset after threshold sweeping under a stricter recall constraint of at least 99%. The figure shows that WSS@99 remained positive across datasets, with the strongest value in Chan_CD011218 and more modest values in Anmarkrud_2022 and Theobald_2021.

Under the stricter WSS@99 constraint, workload saving remained possible but became more dataset-dependent. Table 3 reports the selected-threshold recall, specificity, work-saved rate, true positives, and false negatives underlying these WSS operating points.

Table 3. Selected operating-point statistics for WSS@95 and WSS@99.

Values were calculated at the threshold selected by the recall-constrained sweep for each dataset and target recall level. TP and FN refer to human-labelled INCLUDE records retained and missed at the selected threshold.

Dataset	Target recall	WSS	Recall	Specificity	Work saved	TP	FN
Anmarkrud_2022	95%	0.751	0.953	0.870	0.801	202	10
Anmarkrud_2022	99%	0.376	0.991	0.421	0.386	210	2
Chan_CD011218	95%	0.715	1.000	0.781	0.765	14	0
Chan_CD011218	99%	0.755	1.000	0.781	0.765	14	0
Theobald_2021	95%	0.234	0.950	0.486	0.284	228	12
Theobald_2021	99%	0.094	0.992	0.187	0.104	238	2

Together, these selected operating-point results show that the threshold-tunable hidden-state score can be converted into high-recall workload-saving settings. The next section tests whether these results depended on the true record–label association.

3.4 Shuffle-label controls supported dependence on true screening labels

After selecting the high-recall operating points, we tested whether the observed performance depended on the true record–label association. The shuffle-label control kept the hidden-state features and modeling pipeline fixed but randomly permuted the human screening-stage labels. If similar performance appeared under shuffled labels, the result would be less convincing as evidence of screening-relevant signal in the hidden-state representations.

Figure 6. Shuffle-label control for WSS@95.

Observed WSS@95 values from the primary hidden-state probe are compared with shuffled-label null distributions generated by randomly permuting screening-stage labels while holding the hidden-state features and modeling pipeline fixed. Across all three datasets, observed WSS@95 values were far above the shuffled-label null distributions. This indicates that the primary workload-saving results depended on the real record-label association rather than being reproduced by the same pipeline under randomized labels.

The WSS@95 shuffle-label control supported the central performance claim. The hidden-state probe did not recover comparable high-recall workload-saving performance when the relationship between records and screening-stage labels was broken.

Figure 7. Shuffle-label control for AUROC.

Observed AUROC values from the primary hidden-state probe are compared with shuffled-label null distributions. The shuffled-label distributions were centered near chance-level ranking, whereas the observed AUROC values were consistently higher. This provides a complementary ranking-based sanity check that the probe's ordering of records depended on the true screening labels.

These controls were interpreted as supplementary sanity checks rather than primary performance endpoints. The primary evidence for screening utility remained the out-of-fold WSS@95 and WSS@99 operating-point results. The shuffle-label analyses show that comparable results were not recovered after removing the true label structure. The next section examines how prompt length and linear-probe regularization affected the primary configuration.

3.5 Prompt and regularization comparisons supported the primary linear-readout configuration

After confirming that the primary hidden-state scores were threshold-tunable and depended on the true screening labels, we examined whether performance depended on two design choices: the task-conditioning prompt and the constraint placed on the linear readout. We compared short versus full criteria prompts and two logistic-regression regularization settings, $C = 0.01$ and $C = 1.0$. Because C is inversely related to regularization strength, $C = 0.01$ corresponds to a more strongly regularized and more constrained linear readout.

Figure 8. Prompt-length and regularization comparison for WSS@95.

WSS@95 values are shown for short-criteria and full-criteria prompt settings under two logistic-regression regularization settings. $C=0.01$ represents the stronger-regularization condition and therefore a more constrained linear readout, whereas $C=1.0$ allows a more flexible readout. The short-criteria, $C=0.01$ setting provided the strongest and most consistent WSS@95 performance and was therefore used as the primary hidden-state probe configuration.

The prompt comparison showed that adding more detailed criteria text did not consistently improve high-recall workload saving. In these datasets, concise researcher-curated criteria were sufficient to condition the hidden-state representation for the screening task. This finding should not be interpreted as evidence that short prompts are universally preferable, but it shows that longer eligibility descriptions should not be assumed to improve recall-constrained screening scores.

The regularization comparison also supported the use of a constrained linear readout. The stronger-regularization setting, $C = 0.01$, performed better than or comparable to the more flexible $C = 1.0$ setting in the main WSS@95 comparison. This pattern is consistent with the view that useful screening

signal was readable from the frozen hidden-state representation without requiring a highly flexible downstream head.

On the basis of this ablation, the short-criteria, $C = 0.01$ configuration was retained as the primary hidden-state probe setting. The next section compares this primary configuration with lexical baselines.

3.6 Hidden-state probes exceeded lexical baselines on the primary WSS@95 endpoint

We next compared the primary hidden-state probe with BM25 and TF-IDF to determine whether its recall-constrained workload-saving performance exceeded lexical matching. This comparison tested a stricter version of the central claim: if similar WSS values could be achieved by matching criteria terms to title-and-abstract text, the added value of hidden-state probing would be limited. BM25 served as a transparent term-matching baseline, whereas TF-IDF provided a stronger lexical vector-space baseline.

Figure 9. WSS@95 comparison between the hidden-state probe and lexical baselines.

Bars show WSS@95 for the primary Llama hidden-state probe, BM25, and TF-IDF across the three datasets. WSS@95 was selected using the same recall-constrained threshold-sweep procedure for all methods. The hidden-state probe exceeded both lexical baselines on the primary WSS@95 endpoint in all three datasets, while TF-IDF was consistently more competitive than BM25.

At the primary WSS@95 endpoint, the hidden-state probe outperformed both lexical baselines in every dataset. The BM25 comparison shows that the probe was not merely reproducing transparent criteria-to-record term matching. The TF-IDF comparison is more demanding: TF-IDF recovered substantial lexical screening signal, yet the hidden-state probe still achieved higher WSS@95 across all datasets. This supports the interpretation that the prompt-conditioned hidden-state score provided additional workload-saving utility at the main high-recall operating point.

Figure 10. WSS@99 comparison between the hidden-state probe and lexical baselines.

Bars show WSS@99 for the primary Llama hidden-state probe, BM25, and TF-IDF across the three datasets. WSS@99 used the same threshold-sweep procedure as WSS@95 but required recall of at least 99%. Under this stricter recall constraint, the comparison was more mixed: TF-IDF exceeded the hidden-state probe in Anmarkrud_2022, whereas the hidden-state probe remained higher in Chan_CD011218 and Theobald_2021.

The WSS@99 comparison qualifies the WSS@95 finding. The hidden-state probe was not uniformly superior under every recall constraint, and TF-IDF remained a strong lexical comparator when the recall requirement became stricter. Thus, the baseline results support a focused claim rather than an overgeneral one: the hidden-state probe provided its most consistent advantage on the primary WSS@95 endpoint, while performance at WSS@99 was more dataset-dependent.

Together, these comparisons show that the hidden-state probe added value beyond lexical matching at the main workload-saving endpoint, but they also show that lexical baselines—especially TF-IDF—remain important comparators. The next section examines dataset ceilings, score separation, representation capacity, and score relationships to better interpret why the size of the hidden-state advantage varied across datasets and recall constraints.

3.7 Representation-capacity and heterogeneity diagnostics explained dataset-level variation

The preceding analyses showed that the hidden-state probe improved on lexical baselines at the primary WSS@95 endpoint, but the magnitude of workload saving varied across datasets. We therefore used diagnostic analyses to examine dataset-level limits, score behavior, representation capacity, and overlap with lexical scoring. These analyses were descriptive and were not used as primary performance endpoints.

We first asked whether the datasets differed in their theoretical opportunity for workload saving. Observed WSS@95 was compared with the maximum WSS@95 achievable under a perfect ranking, in which all INCLUDE records were ranked above all EXCLUDE records.

Figure 11. Observed WSS@95 versus theoretical WSS@95 ceiling.

Observed WSS@95 values from the primary hidden-state probe are compared with the maximum WSS@95 achievable under a perfect ranking for each dataset. Labels indicate the observed-to-ceiling ratio. The probe captured a larger share of the theoretical ceiling in Anmarkrud_2022 and Chan_CD011218 than in Theobald_2021, indicating greater remaining ranking difficulty in Theobald_2021.

The ceiling comparison helps explain the cross-dataset pattern. The hidden-state probe captured 86.3%, 76.9%, and 45.9% of the theoretical WSS@95 ceiling in Anmarkrud_2022, Chan_CD011218, and Theobald_2021, respectively. Thus, Theobald_2021 was not only lower in observed WSS@95, but also farther from its dataset-specific ceiling.

We next examined whether the out-of-fold hidden-state probe scores separated human-labelled INCLUDE and EXCLUDE records.

Figure 12. Out-of-fold hidden-state probe scores by human screening label.

Distributions show primary Llama hidden-state probe inclusion scores stratified by human screening-stage label. Higher scores indicate stronger evidence toward INCLUDE according to the supervised probe. The plots show label-dependent score separation, although overlap remained and the degree of separation varied across datasets.

The score distributions show that the out-of-fold probe scores reflected screening-label structure rather than behaving as undifferentiated scores. The weaker separation in Theobald_2021 is consistent with its lower WSS@95 and lower observed-to-ceiling ratio.

Having observed label-dependent separation in the out-of-fold scores, we then asked a representation-capacity question: whether screening-stage labels were linearly readable from the full frozen hidden-state feature space under an in-sample diagnostic.

Table 4. Full-sample linear readout diagnostic of hidden-state representation capacity.

Full-sample linear readouts were fitted and evaluated on the same labelled records to assess whether screening-stage labels were linearly readable from the frozen hidden-state feature space. This diagnostic was used to characterize in-sample representation capacity and strict linear separability, not to estimate out-of-fold or out-of-sample screening performance.

Dataset	Full-sample AUROC	AP	Minimum training error	Strict linear separability
Anmarkrud_2022	1.000	1.000	0	Yes
Chan_CD011218	1.000	1.000	0	Yes
Theobald_2021	1.000	1.000	0	Yes

Distributions show scores from full-sample linear readouts fitted and evaluated on the same labelled records. This analysis was used as a representation-capacity diagnostic rather than as an estimate of generalizable screening performance. The strong in-sample separation indicates that screening-stage labels were linearly readable from the frozen hidden-state feature space under this diagnostic setting.

Full-sample linear readouts showed strong in-sample label-related structure in all three datasets. The weakly regularized full-sample readout achieved perfect in-sample ranking and zero minimum training error, and the strict in-sample linear separability check returned positive results for all datasets. Because fitting and evaluation used the same records, this result was interpreted only as evidence of linearly readable representation structure, not as out-of-fold or out-of-sample screening performance.

We then examined whether the hidden-state scores behaved like lexical scores or captured partly distinct scoring signals.

Figure 13. Relationships between hidden-state probe scores and lexical baseline scores.

Plots compare primary Llama hidden-state probe scores with BM25 and TF-IDF lexical scores across datasets. These relationships describe overlap between scoring systems, not the mechanism by which the LLM formed the hidden-state representation.

The score relationships showed dataset-dependent overlap between hidden-state and lexical scoring. In some datasets, hidden-state and lexical scores ranked records differently, supporting the view that the hidden-state probe was not identical to lexical matching. In other cases, stronger overlap suggested that hidden-state and lexical signals may capture partly shared information. These correlations should therefore be interpreted as descriptive evidence about scoring overlap, not as proof of a specific semantic mechanism.

Finally, we used exploratory geometry diagnostics to assess whether the label structure appeared as a simple global separation in the hidden-state space.

Figure 14. Exploratory PCA projections of hidden-state representations.

PCA was used only to visualize low-dimensional projections of standardized hidden-state vectors. These projections were not used for model fitting, threshold selection, or performance estimation. The panels provide descriptive context for hidden-state geometry but should not be interpreted as mechanistic evidence of eligibility reasoning.

Centroid separation ratios were modest across datasets: 0.480 in Anmarkrud_2022, 0.396 in Chan_CD011218, and 0.398 in Theobald_2021. Together with the PCA projections, this suggests that class structure was not captured by a simple low-dimensional or centroid-level separation alone. This is consistent with the need for a supervised linear readout while cautioning against overinterpreting individual hidden-state dimensions.

Together, these diagnostics support a balanced interpretation. The primary evidence for practical screening utility remained the out-of-fold WSS@95 and WSS@99 operating-point results. The diagnostic analyses showed that hidden-state scores reflected screening-label structure, that the full hidden-state space contained linearly readable label-related information in sample, and that hidden-state scores were not identical to lexical baselines. At the same time, the modest centroid-level separation and exploratory PCA results indicate that these diagnostics should not be treated as mechanistic explanations of eligibility reasoning.

4. Discussion

4.1 Principal findings

This study evaluated whether prompt-conditioned Llama hidden states could be transformed into threshold-sweepable inclusion scores for high-recall title-and-abstract screening. The central contribution is not merely that the probe achieved favorable screening metrics, but that it converted an open-weight LLM representation into a tunable screening signal. Unlike direct prompting approaches that typically return a fixed include/exclude response, the hidden-state probe produced graded scores that could be moved along the recall–workload trade-off. This tunability is the key methodological

contribution of the study: it allows reviewers to select operating points that match explicit recall requirements rather than accepting a single model decision.

Empirically, this workflow produced meaningful high-recall workload savings. At the primary WSS@95 endpoint, the probe achieved WSS values of 0.751, 0.715, and 0.234 across Anmarkrud_2022, Chan_CD011218, and Theobald_2021, respectively. The probe exceeded both BM25 and the stronger TF-IDF lexical baseline on WSS@95 in all three datasets, although TF-IDF remained competitive and exceeded the probe at WSS@99 in Anmarkrud_2022. The results therefore support the feasibility of hidden-state probing for recall-constrained screening, but not a claim of uniform superiority across all metrics, baselines, or recall constraints.

The cross-dataset pattern is also informative. Performance was strongest in Anmarkrud_2022 and Chan_CD011218 and more modest in Theobald_2021, suggesting that dataset-level properties affect how much screening signal can be read out from title-and-abstract representations. Candidate factors include INCLUDE prevalence, the separability or typicality of records, and the degree to which eligibility criteria are expressed in title-and-abstract text. These factors were not experimentally isolated in the present study, so they should be treated as hypotheses for future work rather than as established mechanisms. Overall, the principal finding is that prompt-conditioned hidden-state probes can provide a tunable decision-support signal for high-recall screening, with benefits that are meaningful but dataset- and metric-dependent.

4.2 From generated decisions to auditable representation-based screening scores

Direct prompting treats the LLM as an integrated decision system: the model receives a prompt, forms an internal representation, applies an implicit decision rule, and returns a generated response. This approach can be useful for screening support, but it bundles representation formation, relevance judgement, output generation, and format compliance into a single black-box response. For recall-constrained title-and-abstract screening, this bundling is a limitation because reviewers need more than a single generated include/exclude decision. They need a controllable screening signal whose threshold can be adjusted to preserve sensitivity and manage false-negative risk.

Confidence-like outputs or token probabilities do not fully solve this problem. Even when token probabilities are available, they are generation-token quantities rather than review-specific supervised inclusion scores trained against screening-stage labels. Similarly, prompted confidence statements may be sensitive to wording, output format, and prompt policy. These quantities should therefore not be

assumed to behave like calibrated inclusion probabilities for selecting high-recall operating points. The methodological motivation for hidden-state probing is to replace this implicit generated decision with a score that is learned from the review’s own screening labels.

The hidden-state-probe workflow decomposes the screening process into three explicit stages: representation extraction, supervised score learning, and threshold selection. In this workflow, the LLM is not the screener; it is the source of a task-conditioned representation. The criteria prompt conditions the representation on the review-specific eligibility context, the logistic-regression probe learns a supervised mapping from the hidden-state representation to screening-stage labels, and the threshold sweep converts the resulting score into a human-controlled recall–workload operating point. This design makes the final screening policy an explicit threshold choice rather than an implicit generative decision.

The in-sample linear readout diagnostic illustrates why this decomposition is useful. It allowed us to ask a representation-level question that direct prompting does not expose directly: whether screening-stage labels are linearly readable from the frozen hidden-state space. In the full-sample diagnostic, the primary 4096-dimensional hidden-state features showed strong label-related structure, and the implemented separability check returned strict in-sample linear separability for all three datasets. This result supports the view that the hidden-state space contained screening-relevant structure that could be read out by a supervised linear head. However, because the same records were used for fitting and evaluation, this diagnostic should be interpreted as evidence about representation capacity and in-sample geometry, not as an estimate of out-of-sample screening performance.

The broader value of this decomposition is auditability. By separating representation extraction, supervised scoring, threshold selection, and human review, the workflow makes different sources of performance easier to inspect. Weak performance may reflect limited representation-level separation, insufficient readout generalization, an unfavorable recall–workload trade-off, or dataset-level constraints on achievable workload saving. At the same time, this should not be confused with mechanistic interpretability. Individual hidden-state dimensions remain latent and should not be treated as human-readable eligibility concepts. The contribution is more pragmatic: hidden-state probing turns an internal LLM representation into an empirically testable, threshold-controllable screening score.

4.3 Why WSS@95 and WSS@99 are central to high-recall screening

The intended use case of this workflow is high-recall systematic-review screening, not generic binary classification. This distinction matters because the costs of screening errors are asymmetric. False

positives mainly increase reviewer workload by retaining irrelevant records for further inspection, whereas false negatives may remove eligible studies from the review pipeline. A model that maximizes overall accuracy, or performs well at a default threshold, may still be unsuitable if it misses too many INCLUDE records. For this reason, the relevant operating question is not simply whether the model can classify records correctly, but how much manual screening can be avoided while preserving a prespecified level of recall.

WSS@95 and WSS@99 directly express this workflow objective. They evaluate workload reduction only after imposing high-recall constraints, corresponding to operating points that retain at least 95% or 99% of human-labelled INCLUDE records. In this sense, WSS@95 and WSS@99 are not generic discrimination metrics; they are recall-constrained workload metrics. They translate a graded inclusion score into a practical screening policy by asking: if reviewers require a given level of sensitivity, how many records can be safely deprioritized or spared from full manual screening?

This is why accuracy alone was not treated as the primary endpoint, even though one could choose thresholds that maximize accuracy or other conventional classification criteria. In systematic-review screening, the threshold that maximizes accuracy may be too aggressive if it excludes eligible records, especially in imbalanced datasets where the EXCLUDE class dominates. The primary value of a screening score is therefore not that it yields the highest possible accuracy at a single threshold, but that it supports explicit movement along the recall–workload trade-off. The threshold-sweep procedure makes this trade-off visible and allows the operating point to be selected according to the review’s tolerance for false negatives.

The comparison with TF-IDF illustrates why this distinction matters. TF-IDF was a strong lexical baseline and, in some cases, achieved stronger overall ranking metrics than the hidden-state probe. For example, in Chan_CD011218, TF-IDF achieved higher AUROC and average precision, yet the hidden-state probe achieved higher WSS@95 and WSS@99. This divergence shows that overall ranking quality and high-recall workload-saving behavior are related but not interchangeable. AUROC summarizes pairwise ranking across the full score distribution, and average precision summarizes positive-class ranking across the precision–recall curve. WSS@95 and WSS@99 instead focus on the specific high-recall threshold region where screening decisions would actually be made.

Accordingly, AUROC and average precision remain useful complementary metrics, but they should not replace recall-constrained workload-saving metrics when the intended application is high-

sensitivity screening. The central methodological requirement is a score that can be swept across thresholds and evaluated at reviewer-defined recall targets. WSS@95 and WSS@99 therefore provide the most direct evidence for whether the score is useful in the intended screening workflow.

4.4 Relationship to lexical baseline

The lexical baseline comparisons clarify what the hidden-state probe added and what it did not add. Compared with BM25, the hidden-state probe showed large WSS@95 advantages across all three datasets. Because BM25 is a transparent term-matching baseline between review criteria and title-and-abstract text, this result suggests that the hidden-state probe was not merely reproducing a simple lexical relevance score. The low Llama–BM25 score correlations in Anmarkrud_2022 and Chan_CD011218 further support the view that the hidden-state probe and BM25 often ranked records differently.

The comparison with TF-IDF is more stringent. TF-IDF was a much stronger lexical baseline than BM25 and recovered substantial screening signal from title-and-abstract text. This is important because it prevents the contribution of the hidden-state probe from being overstated. The hidden-state probe exceeded TF-IDF on the primary WSS@95 endpoint in all three datasets, indicating additional workload-saving utility at the main high-recall operating point. However, TF-IDF remained competitive and exceeded the hidden-state probe at WSS@99 in Anmarkrud_2022. The contribution of the hidden-state probe is therefore not that it universally dominates lexical methods, but that it improved the primary recall-constrained workload-saving endpoint even against a stronger lexical baseline.

The score-correlation analyses also suggest a more nuanced relationship between hidden-state and lexical scoring. In some datasets, low correlations between Llama and lexical scores suggest that the hidden-state probe captured screening signals that were not identical to term-weighted lexical matching. In other cases, stronger correlations and weaker workload-saving gains suggest greater overlap between hidden-state and lexical signals, or a dataset in which title-and-abstract eligibility information was harder to separate regardless of scoring method. These correlations should be interpreted as evidence about overlap between scoring systems, not as evidence of a specific semantic mechanism inside the LLM.

These findings have implications for future evaluations of LLM-assisted screening. A comparison against BM25 alone may underestimate what lexical approaches can achieve, especially when TF-IDF or other vector-space methods provide stronger baselines. Future work should therefore compare hidden-state probes not only with transparent lexical baselines such as BM25 and TF-IDF, but also with

dense embedding retrieval models, active-learning screening systems, and hybrid lexical–representation approaches. The value of hidden-state probing should be judged against strong alternatives, and its strongest current claim is improvement on the intended WSS@95 screening endpoint rather than universal superiority across all metrics.

4.5 Prospective use of the method

The practical value of the proposed workflow lies in using a tunable inclusion score to support reviewer-controlled screening triage. The output of the hidden-state probe should not be understood as an autonomous exclusion decision. Rather, it is a graded screening signal that can be converted into an operating policy through threshold selection. Because the present study was retrospective, the workflow implications discussed here should be treated as implementation hypotheses for prospective validation rather than as a validated screening protocol.

In a prospective deployment scenario, a review team could begin with a set of labelled title-and-abstract screening records from the review itself. Hidden-state features would then be extracted using the review-specific criteria prompt, and a supervised probe would be fitted to learn a mapping from hidden-state representations to screening-stage labels. A recall-constrained threshold would be selected using held-out or cross-validated data, with the target recall level chosen according to the review team’s tolerance for false negatives. The resulting score could then be applied to unscreened records to prioritize or deprioritize manual screening effort.

A conservative use case would route low-scoring records into a low-priority audit pool rather than exclude them automatically. Records above the selected threshold could proceed to normal or prioritized human screening, whereas records below the threshold could be delayed, screened with lower priority, or sampled for manual audit. If the audit sample identified INCLUDE records, the review team could lower the threshold, expand manual review of the low-score region, or return that subset to full manual screening. This audit-controlled design would use the model to guide screening intensity while preserving human oversight.

The choice of operating point should depend on the review context. Reviews with very low tolerance for missed studies may require a stricter recall target, such as 99%, combined with a larger audit sample or second-reviewer verification. Reviews with severe workload constraints might consider a 95% recall target, but only with explicit documentation of the threshold-selection procedure and the planned audit process. The method may be most useful for large screening sets with relatively low

INCLUDE prevalence and eligibility cues that are visible in title-and-abstract text. It may be less useful when eligibility depends primarily on full-text information, when few labelled screening records are available, or when INCLUDE and EXCLUDE records are highly similar at the title-and-abstract stage.

Thus, the appropriate prospective use of this workflow is decision support rather than decision replacement. The hidden-state probe can help translate LLM representations into a reviewer-controlled triage policy, but final responsibility for inclusion and exclusion decisions should remain with the review team. Future prospective studies should test whether audit-controlled use of tunable hidden-state scores can reduce workload without producing unacceptable false-negative risk in real screening workflows.

4.6 Limitations and future work

Several limitations define the scope of these findings. First, the three datasets were informative rather than exhaustive. They differed in sample size, INCLUDE prevalence, and apparent screening difficulty, which made them useful for evaluating heterogeneity across screening tasks. However, three datasets are not sufficient to establish general rules about when hidden-state probing will be most effective. The results suggest that dataset-level properties matter, but they do not identify the full set of conditions under which the workflow will generalize. Future work should therefore evaluate larger and more diverse collections of reviews, including different disciplines, search strategies, inclusion prevalences, record-similarity structures, and eligibility-criteria profiles.

Second, the study was retrospective. The out-of-fold design, bootstrap intervals, shuffle-label controls, lexical baselines, and threshold sweeps provide useful evidence about the method under controlled retrospective evaluation. However, they do not fully reproduce a live screening workflow in which labels accumulate over time, reviewers may disagree, eligibility criteria may be refined, and audit decisions may alter the screening process. The prospective audit-controlled workflow described above should therefore be treated as an implementation hypothesis rather than as a validated deployment protocol. Future human-in-the-loop studies are needed to test whether threshold-tunable hidden-state scores can reduce workload without producing unacceptable false-negative risk in real screening practice.

Third, the main configuration should be interpreted as an effective tested setting, not as a proven optimum. The primary analysis used Meta-Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct, short criteria prompts, 4096-token inputs, the final-layer hidden state at the last token, and a regularized logistic-regression probe. These

choices were appropriate for the present study and were supported by the ablation results, but they do not establish that this model, prompt format, layer, token position, input length, or readout head is optimal. Future work should compare alternative prompt formats, no-criteria inputs, different layers and pooling strategies, other open-weight LLMs, and alternative supervised readout models under the same recall-constrained evaluation framework.

Fourth, decomposing the LLM workflow improved auditability but did not eliminate opacity. The hidden-state probe separated representation extraction, supervised scoring, and threshold selection, making the pipeline more observable than a single generated include/exclude response. However, the 4096-dimensional hidden-state vector remains a latent representation. We did not determine which dimensions, directions, or subspaces correspond to specific eligibility concepts, nor did we perform ablation analyses to identify which components of the representation carried the screening signal. The full-sample linear separability diagnostic shows that label-related structure was linearly readable from the hidden-state space, but it does not explain how that structure is organized or why it arises. Similarly, centroid separation, score distributions, and PCA projections are descriptive diagnostics rather than mechanistic explanations. Future work could use layer-wise analyses, feature attribution, subspace methods, and targeted ablations to study which parts of the hidden-state representation contribute to screening performance.

Finally, the baseline and task scope remain bounded. Including both BM25 and TF-IDF made the lexical comparison stronger than a BM25-only evaluation, but it did not cover all relevant alternatives. Dense embedding models, active-learning screening systems, hybrid lexical–representation systems, and matched direct-prompting or API-logprob baselines should be evaluated in future work. In addition, this study focused on title-and-abstract screening-stage labels, not full-text eligibility decisions. That distinction is important because some eligibility information is unavailable in titles and abstracts. The method should therefore be interpreted as support for recall-constrained title-and-abstract screening triage under human oversight, not as a full-text eligibility classifier or an end-to-end systematic-review automation system.

4.7 Conclusion

This study reframed LLM-assisted title-and-abstract screening as a representation-to-score workflow rather than a direct prompting task. Instead of asking the LLM to generate final include/exclude decisions, the workflow extracted prompt-conditioned hidden states, used a supervised probe to convert those representations into graded inclusion scores, and swept thresholds to select recall-

constrained operating points. This design makes the central output a threshold-tunable screening score rather than a single generated decision.

Empirically, the hidden-state probe achieved meaningful WSS@95 across three screening datasets and exceeded both BM25 and TF-IDF lexical baselines on the primary WSS@95 endpoint. At the same time, the findings do not support a claim of uniform superiority across all metrics or datasets. TF-IDF remained a strong baseline, and workload-saving performance was more modest in Theobald_2021. The results therefore support the feasibility of hidden-state probing for high-recall screening, while showing that its benefits are dataset- and metric-dependent.

The method is best understood as human-supervised decision support for recall-constrained screening triage. Prompt-conditioned hidden-state probes can help reviewers prioritize workload, choose explicit recall targets, and audit low-priority records, but they should not replace final human screening decisions. Future prospective studies are needed to test whether this representation-based workflow can reduce reviewer workload safely in real systematic-review screening settings.

Code and data availability

The analysis code, reproducibility documentation, and versioned output files supporting this study are archived on Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20176429>. The archive corresponds to GitHub repository release v1.0.1: <https://github.com/baobao0605/llama-hidden-state-systematic-review-screening/tree/v1.0.1>. The Zenodo archive should be used as the version of record for reproducing the analyses reported in this manuscript.

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Supplementary materials note

Supplementary materials provide additional documentation and diagnostic outputs supporting the main analyses. These include dataset-provenance notes; exact short-criteria and full-criteria prompt texts; full threshold-sweep outputs for the primary hidden-state probe and lexical baselines; supplementary WSS@95, WSS@99, AUROC, and average-precision tables; prompt-length and regularization ablation results; bootstrap confidence-interval summaries and plots; shuffle-label control distributions; score-separation figures for hidden-state and lexical scores; Llama–BM25 and Llama–TF-IDF score-relationship diagnostics; theoretical-ceiling and observed-to-ceiling details; full-sample linear-readout and strict in-sample linear-separability diagnostics; centroid-separation, nearest-centroid, and PCA-based hidden-state geometry analyses; selected high-recall error examples; and reproducibility notes, including tokenization, truncation, model/checkpoint, feature-extraction, script/output documentation, and the archived Zenodo release corresponding to GitHub repository version v1.0.1. These supplementary analyses are intended to support transparency, robustness assessment, and interpretation of dataset heterogeneity. Representation diagnostics are descriptive and should not be interpreted as out-of-sample performance estimates or mechanistic explanations of individual hidden-state dimensions.